

QUANTUM CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF FFPA-1 BRANDED CORROSION INHIBITOR

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Abstract. In this article, the quantum chemical analysis of FFPA-1 brand corrosion inhibitor synthesized based on monoethanolamine, formalin, and orthophosphoric acid is carried out using Avogadro, Hyper Chem 8.01, Asselrys MS Modeling 3.0.1 software, using limited Semi-empirical (UHF) method, using SCF-MO Calculations were performed on an Intel Pro Pentium 1.40 GHz computer using the semi-empirical AM1, MNDO, PM3 and RM1 methods. Molecular geometry optimization was carried out using the Polak-Ribiere (Conjugate gradient) algorithm.

Keywords: monoethanolamine, formalin and orthophosphoric acid, Avogadro, Hyper Chem 8.01, Asselrys.

Introduction

The process of corrosion is a process of chemical and electrochemical as well as biological degradation of metals as a result of environmental effects [1,2]. According to the mechanism of the process, there is chemical, electrochemical, and biochemical corrosion. Corrosion begins at the surface of the metal and spreads deeper with further development of the process. The environment in which metal corrosion occurs is various liquids and gases [3-5]. Various amines, ketones, aliphatic carboxylic acids, and amino acids, as well as products of the interaction of amino alcohols and their derivatives with sulfonamides, carboxylic acids, ethers, and aldehydes, are used as organic inhibitors [6]. Amino acids such as glycine, methionine, and histidine glutamic acid are used as inhibitors against steel corrosion in sulfuric acid, aspartic acid in hydrochloric acid, alanine chloride, and sulfuric acid [7].

Experimental part

Quantum chemical calculation of the reaction property of FFPA-1 brand corrosion inhibitor molecule in Avogadro, Hyper Chem 8.01, Asselrys MS Modeling 3.0.1 by constrained Semi-empirical (UHF) method, using SCF-MO for semi-empirical AM1, MNDO, PM3, and Calculations were performed on an Intel Pro Pentium 1.40 GHz computer using the RM1 method. Molecular geometry optimization was carried out using the Polak-Ribiere (Conjugate gradient) algorithm. These methods make it possible to determine the total energy of the molecule and electron densities of molecular orbitals, as well as the geometric optimization of the studied molecule.

Results and Discussion

One of the important electronic characteristics is the Mulliken effective charges on atoms (CHARGES) and the total energy of the system (TOTAL ENERGY) (Table 3.1).

Based on the results of four selected quantum-chemical calculations, it can be concluded that the high values of the negative effective charge in the FFPA-1 corrosion inhibitor molecule are in the C=O, -OH, N-H, P=O, P-OH groups. indicates that it can form five- and eight-membered chelate compounds.

Table 3.1.

Effective charge distribution in donor atoms of FFPA-1 branded corrosion inhibitor molecules

FFPA-1 corrosion inhibitor			
Calculation method		Calculation method	
AM1		MNDO	
PM3		RM1	

Table 3.1.

Effective charge values of donor atoms in inhibitor molecules

Atoms	AM1, eV	MNDO, eV	PM3, eV	RM1, eV	
xxx					
$\delta_q O^1_{(C=O)}$	-0,464	-0,440	-0,510	-0,474	
$\delta_q O^1_{(O-H)}$	-0,330	-0,324	-0,310	-0,326	
$\delta_q O^2_{(C=O)}$	-0,464	-0,375	-0,415	-0,384	
$\delta_q N^1_{(NH_2)}$	-0,906	-0,595	-0,520	-0,975	
$\delta_q O^1_{(P=O)}$	-1,117	-0,658	-0,862	-1,137	
$\delta_q O^1_{(POH)}$	-0,812	-0,466	-0,694	-0,864	
$\delta_q O^2_{(POH)}$	-0,824	-0,498	-0,700	-0,905	
E	-2690,9462 (kcal/mol)	- 2616,1700 (kcal/mol)	-2673,4993 (kcal/mol)	-1816,1677 (kcal/mol)	

The electron density in the HOMO of Figure 1 is located on the oxygen and secondary nitrogen atoms in the -C=O and P=O groups (Figure 1). The energies of the LUMO and HOMO states are also very different for this ligand. Therefore, Figure 1 also creates a strong field, and according to Pearson's principle of "hard and soft acids and bases", the C=O and P=O groups and the secondary nitrogen atoms compete.

Conclusion

According to the obtained calculation results, based on the results of four selected quantum-chemical calculations, it can be concluded that the highest values of negative effective charge in the XXX molecule are in C=O, -OH, N-H, P=O, and P-OH groups. indicates that these atoms can form five- and eight-membered chelate compounds through coordination bonds with metal.

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